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Flood Resilience, Architectural Design and Housing Development in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The study explored flood resilient, architectural design and housing development in port-harcourt metropolis. The methodology integrates both primary and secondary data sources. With a population of 1,416, a sample frame of 708, and a sample size of 512 determined using the Taro Yamane method, the study employed field observations, surveys, and statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics. Findings on the best measures to make buildings more resilient to pluvial floods highlight a strong consensus on the importance of making buildings more resilient to perennial pluvial floods in Port Harcourt. All respondents (100%) emphasized the need for effective architectural changes and evaluations of how buildings perform during floods. Additionally, 99.2% supported the assessment of current flood strategies, with only a small percentage (0.8%) in disagreement. Findings on how the research findings could impact the way buildings can be designed to withstand floods indicates that every respondent (100%) agreed on the importance of adopting specific design strategies and using new flood-resistant materials. Additionally, 99.6% supported the idea of updating architectural codes and standards to improve flood resilience, with a very small minority (0.4%) opposed. Findings on how City Planning can be influenced by The Research to Better Protect Buildings from Flood highlight strong agreement on how the research findings could improve building designs to withstand floods in the study area. All respondents (100%) emphasized the importance of incorporating flood-resilient designs into city planning and increasing green spaces for better water absorption. Additionally, 99.6% supported revising zoning rules to address flood risks, with only a small minority (0.4%) opposed. Findings on policies that could be recommended based on the research to improve how cities handle floods, considering architectural aspects indicate unanimous support for policies that aim to improve flood management in cities, particularly regarding architectural considerations. All respondents (100%) agreed on the importance of creating flood-resistant building codes, offering rewards for eco-friendly architecture, and implementing stricter land-use regulations. Findings on how the research findings can be practically applied in architectural projects to make buildings more resilient indicate unanimous support for applying research findings in architectural projects to improve flood resilience. All respondents (100%) agreed on the importance of using research-based designs, training architects in flood-resilient practices, and developing guidelines for flood-resilient architecture. These findings highlight the need for integrating evidence-based strategies into architectural practices to ensure buildings are better equipped to withstand flooding. By implementing these approaches, cities can enhance building resilience and effectively address the challenges posed by floods. Thus, these measures are crucial for improving urban resilience and minimizing the impact of flooding on infrastructure. To mitigate recurrent pluvial flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis, a multi-faceted approach involving a combination of architectural adaptation strategies, urban planning, and community engagement is essential. This integrated approach will enable the city to effectively address the complex factors contributing to flooding, while also promoting sustainable urban development. Hence, the development of a comprehensive Flood Resilient Design Framework (FRDF) is crucial, integrating architectural adaptation strategies, stakeholder engagement, and policy recommendations.

Keywords: Flood Resilient, Architectural Design, Housing Development, Port-Harcourt Metropolis

INTRODUCTION

The climate and weather patterns in Port Harcourt are important factors for urban development, particularly regarding infrastructure and public health planning. The city's frequent rainfall requires well-maintained drainage systems to prevent flooding, and its high humidity levels demand adequate housing and sanitation systems to mitigate the spread of diseases. Furthermore, the tropical climate with high temperatures and humidity levels presents challenges in terms of energy consumption, particularly air conditioning, and water management for residents and industries. Urban planners need to consider these climatic factors when designing sustainable urban spaces that accommodate the city's growing population while minimizing environmental impacts.

Urban planning also needs to incorporate the effects of seasonal weather on the city's economy. For instance, the agricultural sector benefits from consistent rainfall, but heavy rains in the rainy season can damage crops, especially in low-lying areas, resulting in loss of revenue. Meanwhile, the oil and gas industry in Port Harcourt has to account for weather disruptions that may delay projects or impact production during the rainy season (Paulinus, Agba & Ekanem, 2015). Sustainable architecture is another essential element in mitigating flooding. This approach includes using eco-friendly building materials, energy-efficient systems, and low-impact construction techniques. Sustainable architecture in Port Harcourt could integrate water collection and recycling systems, solar power, and green roofs to help manage both floodwater and energy use (IPCC, 2022). Moreover, sustainable designs should prioritize the reduction of impervious surfaces, increasing water infiltration into the ground. Climate-resilient architecture, by anticipating the increasing frequency and intensity of rain events due to climate change, ensures that new buildings are capable of withstanding both current and projected flood risks (Sovacool, Kivimaa & Mitchell, 2017).

Coastal floods, resulting from extreme tidal conditions and storm surges, are the leading causes of flooding in low-lying coastal areas (Andrew, Samuel, & Caitlyn, 2020). Fluvial or river floods occur when excessive rainfall or snowmelt causes rivers to overflow, with severity depending on factors such as precipitation, soil saturation, and terrain (Andrew, Samuel & Caitlyn, 2020). Pluvial floods occur when intense rainfall overwhelms urban drainage systems or flows over impervious surfaces, causing water accumulation in urban areas, even those above coastal and river floodplains (Terence, Ayodele & Samuel, 2020). Additionally, in Port Harcourt Metropolis, pluvial flooding accounts for 41% of flooding incidents nationwide (Terence, Ayodele & Samuel, 2020). However, understanding the types and causes of flooding provides clarity for detecting the problems associated with perennial pluvial flooding and identifying architectural adaptation strategies to mitigate its impacts. Therefore, this study seeks to analyze the determinants of flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis, focusing on architectural adaptation strategies to mitigate and curtail perennial pluvial flooding. Hence in systematically reviewing the challenges faced by residents, this study aimed to propose solutions for the recurring flooding issues in the metropolis of Port Harcourt. From the above, this study focused on flood resilient, architectural design and housing development in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

LITERATURE REVIEW

Architectural Design

According to Chima, Amakiri and Sheriff (2024) the importance of designing a carefully styled built environment that has the above qualities is paramount because it will positively influence people's lives (Bergman, 2018). Bergman (2018) advanced that the built environment, overall, plays a vital role in influencing people's lives and their overall performances. Williams (2013) stated that the components of the built environment affect our daily decisions and the way we live our lives. Further to this, Frank and Engelke (2005) explained that the technique used to design and build our environments has significant impacts on the decisions we make, our health, and quality of life. Moreover, Williams (2013) confirms that the design and layout of the built environment can significantly contribute to our psychological and physiological health and wellbeing.

Coastal (Surge) Floods

A coastal flood, as the name suggests, occurs in areas that lie on the coast of a sea, ocean, or other large body of open water. It is typically the result of extreme tidal conditions caused by severe weather. Storm surge — produced when high winds from hurricanes and other storms push water onshore — is the leading cause of coastal flooding and often the greatest threat associated with a tropical storm. In this type of flood, water overwhelms low-lying land and often causes devastating loss of life and property. (Maddox, 2021)

Coastal flooding is categorized into three levels:

1. Minor: A slight amount of beach erosion will occur but no major damage is expected.
2. Moderate: A fair amount of beach erosion will occur as well as damage to some homes and businesses.
3. Major: Serious threat to life and property. Large-scale beach erosion will occur, numerous roads will be flooded, and many structures will be damaged. Citizens should review safety precautions and prepare to evacuate if necessary.

The severity of a coastal flood is determined by several factors, including the strength, size, speed, and direction of the storm. The onshore and offshore topography also plays an important role. To determine the probability and magnitude of a storm surge, coastal flood models consider this information in addition to data from historical storms that have affected the area, as well as the density of nearby development.

Figure 1: Coastal Flood Diagram. Source: Gilliland, (2017).

Fluvial (River) Floods

Fluvial or riverine flooding, occurs when excessive rainfall over an extended period causes a river to exceed its capacity. It can also be caused by heavy snow melt and ice jams. The damage from a river flood can be widespread as the overflow affects smaller rivers downstream, often causing dams and dikes to break and swamp nearby areas. (Maddox, 2021)

There are two main types of riverine flooding:

1. Overbank flooding occurs when the water rises and overflows over the edges of a river or stream. This is the most common and can occur in any size channel — from small streams to huge rivers.

2. Flash flooding is characterized by an intense, high-velocity torrent of water that occurs in an existing river channel with little to no notice. Flash floods are very dangerous and destructive not only because of the force of the water but also the hurtling debris that is often swept up in the flow.

The severity of a river flood is determined by the amount of precipitation in an area, how long it takes for precipitation to accumulate, the previous saturation of local soils, and the terrain surrounding the river system. In flatter areas, floodwater tends to rise more slowly and be more shallow, and it often remains for days. In hilly or mountainous areas, floods can occur within minutes after heavy rain. To determine the probability of river flooding, models consider past precipitation, forecasted precipitation, current river levels, and temperatures.

Figure 2: Depiction of River Floods (Fluvial Floods). Source: Maryna Hlushko, (2021).

Groundwater Floods

Groundwater flooding is a lesser-known type of flooding. It is the emergence of groundwater at the ground surface away from perennial river channels and can also include the rising of groundwater into man-made ground, including basements and other subsurface infrastructure. (Macdonald et al., 2012) Flooding from groundwater can happen when the level of water within the rock or soil underground – known as the water table – rises. When the water table rises and reaches ground level, water starts to seep through to the surface and flooding can happen. This means that water may rise up through floors or underground rooms such as cellars or basements. Water doesn't always appear where you would expect it to - such as valley bottoms – it may also emerge on hillsides (*What Is Groundwater Flooding?*, 2019). Groundwater flooding takes much longer to develop than river flooding, often appearing days, weeks, or even months after heavy or prolonged rainfall. This type of flooding can persist for weeks or even months. It is most common in areas with chalk bedrock but can also occur in places with sand and gravel, like river valleys.

To understand groundwater and basement floods, one needs to first understand groundwater. An estimated 40km³ of water runs across the surface of the earth per year, some of it gets collected in surface reservoirs like rivers and streams that flow back into the ocean while the rest seeps into the ground to recharge groundwater systems or aquifers. There is about 35 times as much water that seeps into the groundwater systems than there is in surface reservoirs. With the increase in frequency and

duration of rainfall due to climate change, groundwater aquifers increase in size by absorbing more water. With increased groundwater comes higher groundwater table or artesian conditions. If the groundwater table exists behind a basement wall, then the wall will be subject to hydrostatic pressure which can force large quantities of water through wall cracks or joints and lead to basement flooding (Brisibe et al., 2021).

Figure 3: Depiction of Groundwater Floods.

Sponge City: Benefits

Sponge cities offer numerous benefits, including reduced flood risk, improved water quality, enhanced biodiversity, mitigated urban heat island effect, and improved public health (Li et al., 2019). The use of green infrastructure in sponge cities can also help to improve air quality, reduce noise pollution, and enhance aesthetic value (Benedict & McMahon, 2006). Additionally, sponge cities can provide opportunities for physical activity, social interaction, and community engagement, which can help to improve public health and well-being (Sallis et al., 2016).

Reduced Flood Risk: One of the primary benefits of sponge cities is the reduced risk of flooding. By incorporating green infrastructure, such as green roofs, rain gardens, and permeable pavements, sponge cities can absorb and filter rainwater, reducing the burden on drainage systems and minimizing the risk of flooding (Fletcher et al., 2015). This can help to protect homes, businesses, and infrastructure from flood damage, reducing economic losses and improving public safety.

Improved Water Quality: Sponge cities can also improve water quality by reducing stormwater runoff and filtering out pollutants and sediments (Li et al., 2019). Green infrastructure, such as green roofs and rain gardens, can absorb and treat stormwater runoff, reducing the amount of pollutants and sediments that enter urban waterways. This can help to improve the quality of urban waterways, making them safer for recreation and aquatic life.

Enhanced Biodiversity: Sponge cities can also enhance biodiversity by providing habitat for urban wildlife and promoting ecosystem services (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Green infrastructure, such as

parks and green spaces, can provide habitat for urban wildlife, such as birds, bees, and butterflies. Additionally, sponge cities can promote ecosystem services, such as pollination, pest control, and climate regulation.

Mitigated Urban Heat Island Effect: Sponge cities can also mitigate the urban heat island effect by reducing the temperature in urban areas (Taha, 1997). Green infrastructure, such as green roofs and urban parks, can provide shade, reduce the amount of impervious surfaces, and promote evapotranspiration, all of which can help to reduce the temperature in urban areas.

Improved Public Health: Sponge cities can also improve public health by providing opportunities for physical activity, social interaction, and community engagement (Sallis et al., 2016). Green infrastructure, such as parks and green spaces, can provide opportunities for physical activity, such as walking, cycling, and playing sports. Additionally, sponge cities can promote social interaction and community engagement, which can help to improve mental health and well-being.

Improved Air Quality: Sponge cities can also improve air quality by reducing air pollution and promoting ecosystem services (Benedict & McMahon, 2006). Green infrastructure, such as green roofs and urban parks, can absorb and filter air pollutants, reducing the amount of particulate matter and other pollutants in the air.

Reduced Noise Pollution: Sponge cities can also reduce noise pollution by providing a natural barrier between urban areas and noise sources (Benedict & McMahon, 2006). Green infrastructure, such as green roofs and urban parks, can provide a natural barrier between urban areas and noise sources, reducing the amount of noise pollution in urban areas.

Enhanced Aesthetic Value: Sponge cities can also enhance aesthetic value by providing a natural and beautiful environment (Benedict & McMahon, 2006). Green infrastructure, such as parks and green spaces, can provide a natural and beautiful environment, enhancing the aesthetic value of urban areas.

Sponge City: Implementation and Challenges

Implementing sponge city initiatives can be challenging, requiring significant investment in infrastructure and community engagement (Li et al., 2019).

Some of the challenges include:

Cost: Implementing green infrastructure can be expensive, requiring significant investment in materials and labor (Fletcher et al., 2015). The cost of implementing green infrastructure can be a significant barrier for cities, particularly those with limited budgets. However, the long-term benefits of green infrastructure, such as reduced flood risk and improved water quality, can outweigh the initial costs.

Community engagement: Sponge city initiatives require community engagement and participation, which can be time-consuming and challenging to achieve (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Community engagement is critical to the success of sponge city initiatives, as it helps to build support and ownership among local residents. However, engaging with the community can be challenging, particularly in cities with diverse populations and competing priorities.

Policy and regulatory frameworks: Sponge city initiatives require supportive policy and regulatory frameworks, which can be lacking in some cities (Li et al., 2019). Policy and regulatory frameworks play a critical role in supporting the implementation of sponge city initiatives. However, in some cities, these frameworks may not be in place, or may even create barriers to implementation.

Maintenance and upkeep: Green infrastructure requires regular maintenance and upkeep, which can be challenging to ensure (Fletcher et al., 2015). Maintenance and upkeep are critical to the long-term effectiveness of green infrastructure. However, ensuring that maintenance and upkeep are carried out regularly can be challenging, particularly in cities with limited resources.

Overcoming these challenges will require innovative solutions and collaborative approaches. Cities can learn from each other's experiences and share best practices in implementing sponge city initiatives. Additionally, cities can engage with local communities, stakeholders, and experts to build support and ownership for sponge city initiatives. Furthermore, cities can also explore innovative financing mechanisms, such as green bonds and public-private partnerships, to support the implementation of sponge city initiatives. Governments can also provide incentives, such as tax credits and grants, to encourage private sector investment in green infrastructure. In conclusion, implementing sponge city

initiatives can be challenging, but with innovative solutions and collaborative approaches, cities can overcome these challenges and create more sustainable and resilient urban environments.

Flood Risk Management (FRM) and Planning

Effective flood risk management in Port Harcourt involves identifying areas prone to pluvial floods and incorporating architectural adaptations to reduce vulnerability. This includes strategies such as elevating buildings to keep them above the floodplain, creating detention ponds, and designing drainage systems that direct water flow away from urban areas (Kundzewicz, Hoozemans & Svensson, 2019). Comprehensive flood risk management involves a cross-disciplinary approach, where architects collaborate with urban planners, engineers, and environmental scientists to design solutions that address both structural and non-structural aspects of flood mitigation (Kundzewicz, Hoozemans & Svensson, 2019). Urban planning must incorporate policies that mandate flood resilience measures, ensuring that new developments adhere to flood-proofing standards.

Integrated Water Management (IWM)

The integration of Integrated Water Management (IWM) in architectural strategies ensures that water systems are designed to manage both stormwater and wastewater. IWM encourages the use of permeable surfaces, retention ponds, and bioswales to capture rainwater and prevent flooding, while also ensuring that the water is reused effectively. However, in designing buildings that contribute to water retention and filtration on-site, Port Harcourt's architecture can play a vital role in flood mitigation. Rainwater harvesting systems, for example, can store runoff for later use, reducing the immediate volume of water flowing into the city's drainage systems during a storm event (Ochoa, González & Latorre, 2022).

Community Engagement in Design

The success of flood resilience strategies depends significantly on community engagement. Participatory design involves the local population in planning processes to ensure that flood mitigation measures are contextually appropriate, acceptable, and sustainable. In Port Harcourt, involving local communities, residents, and stakeholders in architectural decisions can lead to solutions that address local flood patterns and the specific needs of different neighborhoods (Roslan, Ali & Rahman, 2015). Additionally, community-driven solutions often promote greater ownership and ensure long-term maintenance of flood resilience measures.

Policy and Governance

Effective flood mitigation and architectural adaptation require strong policy frameworks and governance mechanisms. In Port Harcourt, local authorities must develop zoning laws and building codes that enforce flood-resistant construction practices. Additionally, urban governance must prioritize the inclusion of flood resilience measures in development plans and urban regeneration projects. Collaboration between different sectors, such as urban planning, environmental management, and infrastructure development, is critical for ensuring that flood resilience becomes an integral part of the city's architecture and urban landscape (Sovacool, Kivimaa & Mitchell, 2017).

In conclusion, The Architectural Adaptation Strategies to Mitigate Perennial Pluvial Floods in Port Harcourt Metropolis involve a multifaceted approach integrating blue-green infrastructure, resilience theory, sustainable design principles, and community engagement. This framework highlights the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in urban planning, emphasizing the role of architecture in adapting to flood risks while enhancing the overall quality of urban life. The framework serves as a guideline for creating a resilient, sustainable, and flood-resistant urban environment in Port Harcourt, helping the city respond effectively to the increasing challenges posed by climate change and urbanization.

Adaptation Strategies

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2007) defines adaptation as the process of adjusting natural or human systems in response to current or anticipated climatic conditions or their effects, with the goal of reducing harm or taking advantage of potential benefits. Adaptation to climate change is generally categorized into two types. The first type, adaptation strategies, involves long-term measures designed to address and prepare for climate change impacts (Thomas et al., 2007). The second

type, coping strategies, consists of short-term actions taken at the household level to mitigate the immediate effects of climate-related events such as floods (Thomas et al., 2007; DFID, 2008).

Adaptation strategies can be further divided into two categories: proactive (or anticipatory) and reactive (De Bruin, 2011). Proactive adaptation involves planning and implementing measures in anticipation of future climate changes, while reactive adaptation involves responding to and managing the impacts of climate change after they have occurred (Shongwe et al., 2014). For example, reactive adaptation might include measures like controlling soil erosion, building irrigation dams, developing new crop varieties, and adjusting planting and harvesting schedules. In contrast, anticipatory adaptation might involve developing climate-resilient crop varieties, conducting research and development, and implementing policy measures such as tax incentives and regulations.

In practice, most adaptation measures tend to be reactive, as they are often implemented in response to problems as they arise rather than in anticipation of future issues (Bierbaum et al., 2013). This tendency reflects the immediate nature of many challenges faced by communities and the need for urgent responses to mitigate their impacts.

According to Brody et al. (2009), structural mitigation strategies involve the construction or modification of physical infrastructure to protect people, buildings, and the environment from the impacts of flooding. These strategies are designed to prevent or minimize the intrusion of floodwaters into areas where they could cause damage, effectively serving as barriers between the water and the built environment. The effectiveness of these structural measures in reducing flood damage has been supported by various studies (IPCC, 2014; Queensland Government, 2018). Such strategies aim to manage flood damage by controlling factors such as water height, flow rate, and seepage into structures (Queensland Government, 2018).

Structural and Non-Structural Measures

Structural and non-structural measures are not limited to just mitigation strategies. They play roles in various stages of disaster management, including preparedness, response, and recovery.

Structural Measures

Examples of structural mitigation strategies include the construction of dams, levees, sea walls, and detention basins. Other techniques involve modifying natural and artificial waterways, such as widening, deepening, or realigning canals, rivers, and floodplains, as well as dredging rivers and lakes and building embankments. These measures require significant financial investment and are often implemented by government agencies or through collaborative efforts between communities and authorities (IPCC, 2014; Queensland Government, 2018).

Ologunorisa (2010) categorizes structural flood mitigation strategies into three main types. The first category encompasses engineering schemes, which include both small-scale interventions, such as minor embankments and soil retention measures, and large-scale projects, such as major flood control infrastructure, significant sea walls, and substantial dam constructions. The second category consists of flood abatement schemes, which utilize natural methods, such as afforestation, to manage land use and mitigate flood impacts. These schemes aim to manage flood runoff at the upstream catchment level to reduce its downstream effects (Ologunorisa, 2010). The third category is flood-protection schemes, which focus on modifications to buildings to enhance their resilience to flooding. These can include both permanent and temporary alterations to a building's structure and design to withstand flood conditions, often referred to as building adaptation strategies (Ologunorisa, 2010).

Non-Structural Measures

In contrast, non-structural mitigation strategies are policies and regulatory measures designed to manage flood risks through planning and prevention rather than physical construction. These strategies focus on regulating land use and reducing the exposure of people and assets to flood hazards. Non-structural measures include floodplain zoning, flood insurance, public relief funds, flood forecasting and warning systems, weather modification, and loss-bearing and acceptance (Ologunorisa, 2010). These approaches have been adopted in various countries around the world to complement structural measures and provide a comprehensive approach to flood management (Creach et al., 2020; Queensland Government, 2018; Brody et al., 2009).

Additional non-structural strategies involve evacuation plans, relocation efforts, and other measures aimed at moving people and property out of harm's way during flood events. These strategies are crucial for minimizing the risk to human lives and reducing property damage when floods occur (Lumbroso & Davison, 2016; Kolen, Slomp & Jonkman, 2013; Priest, 2007). By integrating both structural and non-structural approaches, communities can better prepare for, respond to, and recover from flooding, thereby enhancing overall resilience to these natural hazards.

Use of Storm water Tree Trench

A stormwater tree trench is an effective technique to collect and filter stormwater runoff (Cunningham, 2017). This is achieved by a line of trees that are planted in an engineered trench that is designed to hold and infiltrate runoff (Dayton, 2013). The trees appear like any other planted tree on the surface level, however, they are planted in a trench that is specially engineered with layers of soil and gravel (Lefevre et al., 2016). The trench filters and temporarily stores stormwater runoff, allowing it to slowly infiltrate into the ground (Cunningham, 2017). By doing so, stormwater tree trenches improve water quality and reduce the volume of runoff, providing multiple benefits (Dayton, 2013). These trenches are increasingly being used as a green infrastructure practice to help reduce the negative impacts of urbanization on natural hydrologic systems (EPA, 2017).

Figure 5: Section through a Stormwater Tree Trench (Source: Winchester, 2025).

Use of Retention Pond

A way to manage stormwater is through the implementation of a retention pond (EPA, 2017). It is considered a more traditional type of stormwater infrastructure, which has been integrated into grey infrastructure design (Schueler, 1994). A retention pond is an engineered basin designed to store runoff and release it at a controlled rate while maintaining a level of ponded water (Wu et al., 2016). The basin is designed to reduce pollutants and sediment loads as the runoff is retained in the pond (Hunt et al., 2017). Adding sustainable elements to the design of retention ponds can increase water quality and decrease peak discharges (Dietz, 2007). Vegetated forebays may be added to increase sediment removal as well as provide habitat (Brunner et al., 2017). A further improvement to traditional retention ponds is the use of an iron-enhanced sand filter bench that removes dissolved substances such as phosphorus from runoff (Collins et al., 2010). Retention ponds have been widely used as a stormwater management

practice (EPA, 2017). They are designed to temporarily store stormwater and allow pollutants and suspended solids to settle out before the water is released into waterways (Wu et al., 2016). The basin can also provide recreational benefits and enhance the aesthetics of the surrounding environment (Dietz, 2007). However, the effectiveness of retention ponds can be limited by their size, and they may not provide long-term water quality benefits (Hunt et al., 2017). Adding sustainable elements to the design of retention ponds can help improve their overall effectiveness (Brunner et al., 2017). For example, using a vegetated forebay can increase sediment removal, while the use of an iron-enhanced sand filter bench can help remove dissolved substances such as phosphorus from runoff (Collins et al., 2010).

Figure 6: Section Through a Stormwater Retention Pond (Source: Western Environmental Liner, 2020).

Use of Extended Detention Wetlands

Extended detention wetlands are a valuable green infrastructure practice that can provide a range of benefits including flood mitigation, water quality improvement, and ecological benefits (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). These wetlands are designed to store floodwater during a storm and release it slowly to reduce peak flows, which can help to prevent flooding (Wu et al., 2016). The extended detention period provides additional flood storage capacity while also enhancing water quality and providing ecological benefits (Hunt et al., 2017). Extended detention wetlands can be created, restored, or enhanced existing wetlands (EPA, 2017). These wetlands are typically designed as a flood mitigation strategy but can also provide ecological and water quality benefits (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Although extended detention wetlands can require large land areas, they offer significant flood storage benefits (Wu et al., 2016). As stormwater flows into the wetland, it is slowed down and allowed to remain in the wetland area for an extended period (Hunt et al., 2017). This extended detention period enables the wetland to provide increased flood storage and water quality benefits (EPA, 2017). Extended detention wetlands are different from the preservation of existing wetlands, but the two practices are often considered together as part of a watershed-based strategy (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Wetlands can be enhanced to create an extended detention period, which provides additional flood storage capacity while also improving water quality and providing ecological benefits (Wu et al., 2016). Enhancements such as adding vegetation and creating shallow pools can also increase the ecological value of the wetland (Hunt et al., 2017). The vegetation in the wetland can remove pollutants from the water, while the shallow pools can provide a habitat for aquatic wildlife (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Wetlands are densely vegetated water bodies that use sedimentation and filtration to provide treatment of surface water runoff (EPA, 2017). Wetlands generally consist of an inlet zone (sediment basin) a macrophyte zone, which is a shallow, densely vegetated area; and a high-flow bypass channel, which is typically a wide vegetated swale from the inlet pond around the side of the wetland (Wu et al., 2016). Wherever

possible wetlands should be the last stage of the SuDS management train and should be one of the last treatment stages, otherwise, there's a risk of extensive siltation (unless there is upstream treatment) (Hunt et al., 2017). They remove fine sediments, metals, particulates, and dissolved nutrients (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Wetlands mainly treat polluted runoff, provide attenuation, and deliver biodiversity and amenity (EPA, 2017). Increasingly they're also being used as a valuable educational resource (Wu et al., 2016). Wetlands can be constructed on a variety of scales (Hunt et al., 2017). In highly urbanized areas, wetlands can have a hard edge or be part of the streetscape or other hard landscaping features and furniture (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). They must be appropriately sized for the catchment to ensure the hydraulics support water treatment (EPA, 2017). Upstream components both control the flow and level of siltation allowing wetlands and ponds to polish the runoff (Wu et al., 2016). This is achieved by ensuring water flows slowly through the wetland over an extended period of time (known as the residence time) (Hunt et al., 2017). An important mechanism is also the breakdown of oils by natural organisms (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). They need a good supply of oxygen which means the permanent water must be shallow enough so that oxygen can reach the bottom of the wetland (EPA, 2017).

Figure 7: Section Through a Constructed Extended Detention Wetland
(Source: WSUD Engineering, 2012).

Challenges and Limitations of Architectural Adaptation Strategies

Despite the potential benefits of architectural adaptation strategies, several challenges and limitations have been identified. One major challenge is the high initial cost of implementing these strategies, which may make them unaffordable for many people and organizations (Efe and Opoko, 2020). In addition, there is often a lack of public awareness and acceptance of these strategies, which may limit their effectiveness (Akande et al., 2020). Other challenges include limited space availability, the need for regular maintenance and monitoring, and the potential for unintended consequences such as increased air pollution from blue roofs (Sarai and Oloke, 2021).

Policy and Governance Implications

The success of architectural adaptation strategies in mitigating perennial pluvial flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis depends on effective policy and governance. Researchers have emphasized the importance of stakeholder engagement, multi-sectoral collaboration, and the development of regulatory frameworks that promote resilient urban design and construction practices. For example, Enaruvbe et al. (2021) argue that effective governance requires the involvement of all stakeholders, including government agencies, NGOs, and community groups, in decision-making processes related to flood management. Additionally, they suggest the need for regulations and incentives to promote the adoption of architectural adaptation strategies. Overall, the existing literature on architectural adaptation strategies to mitigate perennial pluvial floods in Port Harcourt Metropolis provided valuable insights into the challenges, limitations, and opportunities associated with flood management in the city. However,

further research is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of these strategies in the local context and to explore the potential for their integration with other approaches such as nature-based solutions.

Urban Drainage and Water Management Systems

Perennial pluvial flooding is a recurring problem in urban areas, causing damage to infrastructure, disrupting economic activities, and posing health risks to residents (Marsalek et al., 2016). Urban drainage and water management systems play a critical role in curbing perennial pluvial flooding by managing stormwater runoff and preventing flooding (EPA, 2017). This empirical review section provides an overview of urban drainage and water management systems as they relate to curbing perennial pluvial flooding, including their components, functions, challenges, and innovative solutions.

Components of Urban Drainage and Water Management Systems for Curbing Perennial Pluvial Flooding

Urban drainage and water management systems for curbing perennial pluvial flooding consist of various components, including:

- 1. Stormwater drainage systems:** These systems collect and convey stormwater runoff from urban surfaces, such as roads, sidewalks, and buildings (Wu et al., 2016).
- 2. Green infrastructure:** This includes natural or engineered systems that mimic natural processes to manage stormwater runoff, such as green roofs, rain gardens, and urban wetlands (EPA, 2017).
- 3. Flood control structures:** These structures, such as levees, dams, and floodwalls, help prevent flooding by controlling the flow of stormwater runoff (Marsalek et al., 2016).
- 4. Water treatment plants:** These facilities treat wastewater and stormwater runoff to remove pollutants and contaminants before discharging the treated water into waterways (Metcalf & Eddy, 2014).

METHODOLOGY

Design

The quantitative component of the study provides objective data to complement the qualitative findings and offer statistical evidence on flood risks and mitigation strategies. Surveys were administered to residents, property owners, and local government officials in flood-prone areas of Port Harcourt Metropolis. The survey gathers data on the level of awareness among residents about pluvial flooding, current flood mitigation measures in place, and their views on various architectural strategies for flood prevention. The survey used a mix of Likert scale questions to measure attitudes and perceptions, along with close-ended questions. This approach allows for the quantification of public knowledge and opinions, as well as the identification of patterns in attitudes towards flood resilience. In addition, spatial analysis and mapping using Geographic Information System (GIS) tools was employed to map stratified flood-prone areas in Port Harcourt Metropolis, and analyze the relationship between urban development patterns, existing infrastructure, and the architectural features that influence flooding. Finally, the study incorporates flood impact data analysis. This was involved doing an urban flood vulnerability assessment of the selected areas in Port Harcourt Metropolis. It is essential for developing effective flood risk reduction and management strategies. Statistical tools will be used to analyze this data and explore the relationship between specific architectural features and the occurrence of flooding.

Population and Sampling

The targeted population for the study on Architectural Adaptation Strategies to Mitigate Perennial Pluvial Floods in Port Harcourt Metropolis includes various stakeholders and groups directly or indirectly involved in addressing pluvial flooding challenges.

Residents of Flood-Prone Areas: Based on the work of Wizer & Mpigi, (2020) on the 25 most-flooded roads in Port Harcourt Metropolis. 13 regions (streets/roads) were chosen from the 25 most-flooded roads/streets in Port Harcourt Metropolis. 4 streets/roads were chosen from low-flooded areas, 5 from moderately-flooded areas, and 4 from high-flooded areas. A total of 13 streets/roads were considered for this research. However, Residents from these 13 selected flood-prone areas in Port Harcourt Metropolis form a key part of the population. These individuals provided valuable insights into local experiences

with flooding, awareness of flood risks, and opinions on both existing and potential architectural strategies for flood mitigation. From each of the 13 areas, 20 compounds were selected, with one respondent per compound, resulting in a total of 260 respondents from this group.

Urban Planners and Architects: Professionals such as urban planners and architects are integral to the study, offering expert opinions on design and urban development strategies aimed at reducing flood risks. The research focuses on members of the Nigerian Institute of Town Planners (Rivers State branch), which has 570 members, and the Nigerian Institute of Architects (Rivers State branch), comprising 240 fully registered members. These professionals provide insights into the most effective architectural solutions for mitigating pluvial flooding.

Government Officials: Officials from relevant state ministries in Port Harcourt also form part of the population. These include the Rivers State Ministry of Urban Development and Physical Planning, with 84 staff members, River State Ministry of Housing with 134 staff, and the Rivers State Ministry of Environment, with 102 staff members. Their perspectives on flood management practices, policies, and regulations are crucial for understanding the institutional framework required to implement architectural adaptation strategies.

Community Leaders: Community leaders from the 13 selected flood-prone areas were included to represent the views of the broader community. These leaders play a critical role in advocating for local concerns and influencing decision-making processes related to flood mitigation, two leader or such as street chairman and a member were selected from each flood area, making a total of 26 stakeholders in this category.

Sample Frame

The sample frame for this study, "Architectural Adaptation Strategies to Mitigate Perennial Pluvial Floods in Port Harcourt Metropolis", was thoughtfully developed to include a broad range of stakeholders with diverse roles and experiences related to flood mitigation. The approach ensures a balanced representation of opinions from individuals and institutions who are directly impacted or involved in addressing flooding challenges in the metropolis. The sample was selected by taking 50% of the total population from six key stakeholder groups.

Residents of flood-prone areas constitute a significant portion of the sample frame, with 130 participants selected from a population of 260. This group provides firsthand accounts of the flooding issues they face, offering valuable insights into the effectiveness of existing measures and highlighting the areas requiring improvement for better flood resilience.

The Nigerian Institute of Town Planners (Rivers State Branch) represents the largest group in the sample, with 285 participants selected out of 570. Town planners bring critical expertise to the study as they are responsible for urban development and zoning regulations. Their contributions help evaluate how planning practices can mitigate flooding in urban areas.

The Nigerian Institute of Architects also play a crucial role, contributing 120 participants from its total membership of 240. Architects are vital in designing buildings and infrastructure to withstand flooding. Their input focuses on assessing existing designs and recommending solutions tailored to the challenges posed by recurrent pluvial flooding in the region.

Officials from the Rivers State Ministry of Urban Development and Physical Planning are also included, with 42 selected from a population of 84. This group represents government involvement in urban planning and policy-making, ensuring that the study reflects institutional perspectives and strategies currently in place to manage urban flooding.

The Rivers State Ministry of Environment contributes 51 participants from a population of 102. Their expertise provides an understanding of the environmental dimensions of flooding, including its causes, impacts, and the role of sustainable practices in mitigating its effects.

The Rivers State Ministry of Housing contributes 67 participants from a total population of 134. Their specialized knowledge offers valuable insights into the environmental aspects of flooding, encompassing its underlying causes, consequences, and the importance of sustainable practices in addressing its challenges.

Finally, community leaders from flood-prone areas are represented by 13 individuals from a total of 26. These leaders provide collective insights on how floods affect local communities and the social and cultural dimensions of flood management. Their involvement ensures that community needs and priorities are well-represented in the findings.

In total, the sample frame includes 708 participants, drawn from a population of 1,416 across the seven stakeholder groups. By incorporating inputs from residents, professionals, government agencies, and community leaders, the study ensures a comprehensive understanding of the flooding problem. This diversity strengthens the analysis and helps develop practical, inclusive, and sustainable architectural strategies to address pluvial flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Sample size

The sample size for the research Architectural Adaptation Strategies to Mitigate Perennial Pluvial Floods in Port Harcourt Metropolis was determined using the Taro Yamane formula. This statistical approach ensures the selection of a representative sample that accurately reflects the target population while minimizing sampling error. The study drew participants from seven key stakeholder groups, resulting in a total sample size of 512 individuals from an initial sample frame of 708. The Formula for Taro Yamane method is statistically given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(\epsilon)^2}$$

Where n = sample size

N = Population size

e = Level of significance or allowable error

1 = a constant

However, for each stakeholder, the estimated sample size was obtained for the sample frame of the population, for example, using the residents of flood prone area with a sample frame of 130 stakeholder for illustration, the Taro Yamane formula is thus substituted.

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{130}{1 + 130 (0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{130}{1 + 130 (0.0025)} \\ &= \frac{130}{1.325} = 98 \end{aligned}$$

The Residents of Flood-Prone Areas constituted a significant portion of the sample size, with 98 participants selected from a sample frame of 130. The Nigerian Institute of Town Planners, Rivers State Branch had the largest sample frame of 285 members, from which 166 were selected. From the Nigerian Institute of Architects (Full Members), 92 individuals were selected from a sample frame of 120. The Rivers State Ministry of Urban Development and Physical Planning had a sample frame of 42 participants, with 41 selected for the study. The Rivers State Ministry of Environment had a sample size of 45 individuals, drawn from a sample frame of 51. While the Rivers State Ministry of Housing has a sample size of 57 selected from a sample frame of 67. Finally, the Community Leaders of Flood-Prone Areas, representing grassroots stakeholders, had all 13 members included in the sample size. In summary, the total sample size of 512 participants encompassed a diverse range of stakeholders, ensuring the study benefited from a broad spectrum of expertise, experiences, and perspectives. This approach enhances the reliability of the findings and supports the development of effective architectural adaptation strategies to mitigate pluvial flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

This section outlines the instrumentation and data collection methods employed in this research, including the design and administration of surveys, interviews, and observational studies. The data collection instruments were carefully developed and validated to ensure that they captured the necessary information to address the research questions and objectives. This chapter provides an overview of the

data collection process, including data collection techniques, and instrumentation used to gather both qualitative and quantitative data.

Instrumentation

This research utilized a variety of tools to collect comprehensive data on strategies for architectural adaptation to address recurring urban floods in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The instruments employed included well-structured questionnaires, interviews, and Geographic Information System (GIS) tools, each tailored to extract specific information from relevant stakeholders actively involved in flood management in the city. The structured questionnaire served as the main instrument for data collection, featuring both closed and open-ended questions. Its purpose was to gather diverse insights from key groups such as government officials, urban developers, architects, residents of affected neighborhoods, and community leaders in areas susceptible to flooding. The questionnaire was organized into sections.

Data Collection

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative methods to gain an understanding of flood risks and mitigation strategies. Field Observations focused on flood-prone areas, examining drainage systems, building elevations, and construction materials, providing a baseline for adaptation strategies. Document Review was conducted using government reports, urban planning documents, and flood management policies to understand the historical and policy context of flood mitigation in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Additionally, Surveys were used to gather both expert and community perspectives. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with professionals, including architects, urban planners, and flood management experts, to gain expert insights into effective architectural strategies. Focus group discussions with community leaders were held to explore local views on current flood mitigation measures and potential solutions. Surveys were distributed to residents, property owners, and local government officials to assess their awareness of pluvial flooding and their opinions on architectural strategies for flood prevention. The surveys combined Likert-scale and close-ended questions, providing statistical data on public knowledge and attitudes.

Analytical Techniques for Data Collected/ / Analysis

The data obtained from the survey and GIS assessments were carefully organized and prepared for analysis. Responses from the structured questionnaire were initially sorted according to the demographic characteristics of respondents and the study's key research objectives. Descriptive statistical techniques, such as frequency distributions, percentages, and graphical representations, were utilized to interpret the responses. These methods facilitated the identification of participants' views on recurrent pluvial flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis. In addition, spatial data analysis was conducted using ArcGIS. The GIS software was instrumental in visualizing and analyzing specific flood-prone areas within the study region. However, in mapping these vulnerable locations, ArcGIS provided valuable spatial context to the survey findings, enabling an understanding of the challenges and solutions related to pluvial flood mitigation in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The integration of descriptive statistics and GIS analysis ensured that the data was examined from multiple perspectives, contributing to well-rounded insights into strategies for addressing flooding issues in the study area.

Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

To guarantee the accuracy and dependability of the tools used in this study, a thorough validation process was undertaken. The consistency of the structured questionnaire was evaluated using the test-retest technique. This approach involved administering the same set of questions to a small group of urban planners and other relevant stakeholders within Port Harcourt Metropolis at two different times. This allowed for an assessment of the uniformity in responses, ensuring the questionnaire effectively captured participants' views and experiences related to pluvial flooding and its mitigation. The variations observed between the two rounds of responses were reviewed, and modifications were made to improve the questionnaire's reliability. Additionally, the GIS tools utilized in this research, particularly ArcGIS, were rigorously tested by a certified GIS specialist before being deployed for data collection. This preliminary evaluation ensured the software's capability to accurately extract and analyze spatial data related to pluvial flooding within the study area. The GIS tools were also assessed to confirm their reliability in providing consistent results throughout the study. This step was critical in verifying that the

spatial data collected was both precise and dependable. However, in employing the test-retest method for the questionnaire and subjecting the GIS tools to expert evaluation, the study ensured that all research instruments were both valid and robust. These efforts ensured the collection of high-quality, reliable data that was essential for developing effective architectural strategies to mitigate recurring pluvial flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The combined validation process enhanced the credibility of the research findings and supported the study's objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: How to Make Buildings More Resilient to Perennial Pluvial Floods

S/N	Options	Response		
		Yes	No	Total
1.	Effective architectural changes	100	0	100
2.	Assessment of current flood strategies	99.2	0.8	100
3.	Evaluation of how buildings perform during floods	100	0	100

Source: Researcher, 2025

Table 1 presents the best measures to make buildings more resilient to pluvial floods. However, the results indicate broad agreement on the need for measures to increase building resilience to recurring pluvial floods in Port Harcourt. Every respondent (100%) emphasized the importance of implementing effective architectural changes and evaluating how buildings perform during flood events. Furthermore, 99.2% of respondents supported the assessment of existing flood strategies, with only a small portion (0.8%) opposing it. This highlights the need for ongoing improvements in building design and infrastructure, as well as the continuous evaluation of current flood mitigation efforts, to ensure that structures remain resilient to the frequent flooding challenges in the area.

Table 2: How the Research Findings Could Impact the Way Buildings Can Be Designed to Withstand Floods

S/N	Options	Response		
		Yes	No	Total
1.	Adoption of specific design ideas	100	0	100
2.	Use of new flood-resistant materials	100	0	100
3.	Changes to architectural codes and standards	99.6	0.4	100

Source: Researcher, 2025

Table 2: presents how the research findings could impact the way buildings can be designed to withstand floods. The results reflect a strong consensus on how the research findings could influence the design of buildings to better withstand floods. Every respondent (100%) agreed on the importance of adopting specific design strategies and using new flood-resistant materials. Additionally, 99.6% supported the idea of updating architectural codes and standards to improve flood resilience, with a very small minority (0.4%) opposed. These findings highlight the necessity of incorporating innovative design approaches, advanced materials, and revised building regulations to enhance the ability of structures to resist flood impacts, emphasizing proactive changes in flood-prone areas.

Table 3: How the Research Findings Could Impact the Way Buildings Can Be Designed to Withstand Floods

S/N	Options	Response		
		Yes	No	Total
1.	Including flood-resilient designs in city planning	100	0	100
2.	Creating more green spaces for water absorption	100	0	100
3.	Changing zoning rules	99.6	0.4	100

Source: Researcher, 2025

Table 3: presents how City Planning can be influenced by The Research to Better Protect Buildings from Flood. The results show a unanimous agreement on the impact of the research findings on building design in the study area to withstand floods. All respondents (100%) agreed on the importance of

integrating flood-resilient designs into city planning and creating more green spaces for water absorption. Furthermore, 99.6% supported the modification of zoning rules to better address flood risks, with only a small minority (0.4%) in disagreement. These findings underline the necessity of incorporating flood-resilient design strategies, promoting green spaces, and adjusting zoning regulations to enhance flood resilience and reduce the impact of flooding in vulnerable areas.

Table 4: What Policies Do You Think Should Be Recommended Based On the Research to Improve How Cities Handle Floods, Considering Architectural Aspects

S/N	Options	Response		
		Yes	No	Total
1.	Creating flood-resistant building codes	100	0	100
2.	Offering rewards for eco-friendly architecture	100	0	100
3.	Making land-use rules stricter	100	0	100

Source: Researcher, 2025

Table 4: presents policies that could be recommended based on the research to improve how cities handle floods, considering architectural aspects. The results indicate unanimous support for several policies aimed at improving how cities handle floods, with a focus on architectural aspects. Every respondent (100%) agreed on the importance of creating flood-resistant building codes, providing incentives for eco-friendly architecture, and enforcing stricter land-use regulations. These findings emphasize the necessity for policies that foster resilience to flooding by promoting sustainable building practices and ensuring stricter control over land use. Such measures would not only reduce the risk of flood damage but also encourage environmentally responsible urban development, improving cities' overall flood management strategies.

Table 5: How Research Findings Can Be Practically Applied in Architectural Projects to Make Buildings More Resilient to Floods

S/N	Options	Response		
		Yes	No	Total
1.	Using research-based designs	100	0	100
2.	Training architects in flood-resilient practices	100	0	100
3.	Developing guidelines for flood-resilient architecture	100	0	100

Source: Researcher, 2025

Table 5 presents how the research findings can be practically applied in architectural projects to make buildings more resilient. The results show complete agreement on the practical applications of the research findings to make buildings more resilient to floods. All respondents (100%) supported the use of research-based designs, training architects in flood-resilient practices, and developing guidelines for flood-resilient architecture. This suggests that incorporating these strategies into architectural practice is essential for enhancing the flood resilience of buildings. By adopting research-driven designs, equipping architects with specialized training, and establishing comprehensive guidelines, cities can ensure that buildings are better prepared to withstand the impacts of flooding, leading to improved overall resilience in urban areas.

DISCUSSION

This study tried to propose a Flood Resilient Design Framework (FRDF) tailored to Port Harcourt Metropolis, which integrates innovative architectural adaptation strategies, stakeholder involvement, and actionable policy recommendations to enhance urban resilience and minimize flood-related risks. Findings on the best measures to make buildings more resilient to pluvial floods highlight a strong consensus on the importance of making buildings more resilient to perennial pluvial floods in Port Harcourt. All respondents (100%) emphasized the need for effective architectural changes and evaluations of how buildings perform during floods. Additionally, 99.2% supported the assessment of current flood strategies, with only a small percentage (0.8%) in disagreement. This indicates that both architectural interventions and the continuous evaluation of existing flood mitigation measures are

essential to enhance building resilience against frequent flooding in the metropolis, ensuring better protection for structures in flood-prone areas.

Findings on how the research findings could impact the way buildings can be designed to withstand floods indicates that every respondent (100%) agreed on the importance of adopting specific design strategies and using new flood-resistant materials. Additionally, 99.6% supported the idea of updating architectural codes and standards to improve flood resilience, with a very small minority (0.4%) opposed. These findings highlight the necessity of incorporating innovative design approaches, advanced materials, and revised building regulations to enhance the ability of structures to resist flood impacts, emphasizing proactive changes in flood-prone areas.

Findings on how City Planning can be influenced by The Research to Better Protect Buildings from Flood highlight strong agreement on how the research findings could improve building designs to withstand floods in the study area. All respondents (100%) emphasized the importance of incorporating flood-resilient designs into city planning and increasing green spaces for better water absorption. Additionally, 99.6% supported revising zoning rules to address flood risks, with only a small minority (0.4%) opposed. These findings suggest that integrating flood-resilient strategies, expanding green spaces, and adjusting zoning regulations are essential steps to enhance infrastructure resilience and reduce the impact of flooding in flood-prone areas, promoting sustainable urban development.

Findings on policies that could be recommended based on the research to improve how cities handle floods, considering architectural aspects indicate unanimous support for policies that aim to improve flood management in cities, particularly regarding architectural considerations. All respondents (100%) agreed on the importance of creating flood-resistant building codes, offering rewards for eco-friendly architecture, and implementing stricter land-use regulations. These findings suggest that such policies are crucial in fostering urban resilience to flooding. Thus, in promoting sustainable building practices, incentivizing eco-friendly designs, and regulating land use, cities can better manage flood risks and ensure long-term protection. These measures will enhance flood resilience while encouraging more sustainable urban development.

Findings on how the research findings can be practically applied in architectural projects to make buildings more resilient indicate unanimous support for applying research findings in architectural projects to improve flood resilience. All respondents (100%) agreed on the importance of using research-based designs, training architects in flood-resilient practices, and developing guidelines for flood-resilient architecture. These findings highlight the need for integrating evidence-based strategies into architectural practices to ensure buildings are better equipped to withstand flooding. By implementing these approaches, cities can enhance building resilience and effectively address the challenges posed by floods. Thus, these measures are crucial for improving urban resilience and minimizing the impact of flooding on infrastructure.

CONCLUSION

To address these issues, the study proposed a flood-resilient design framework that incorporates architectural innovations, effective stakeholder involvement, and strong policy measures. Thus in enhancing public awareness, fostering community participation, and prioritizing sustainable urban planning practices, Port Harcourt Metropolis can better manage and mitigate the impacts of perennial pluvial floods while building a more resilient urban environment. As the frequency and severity of flooding events continue to rise, it has become increasingly important to develop effective strategies for mitigating flood risk in residential areas. One promising approach is the implementation of Blue-Green Infrastructure (BGI) in residential buildings. BGI combines natural systems with urban planning to reduce stormwater runoff, improve water quality, and enhance urban livability. This guide provides practical guidance on implementing BGI in residential buildings, with the aim of promoting flood resilience and creating more sustainable and resilient communities. It applies to new and existing residential buildings in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. To mitigate recurrent pluvial flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis, a multi-faceted approach involving a combination of architectural adaptation strategies, urban planning, and community engagement is essential. This integrated approach will enable the city to effectively address the complex factors contributing to flooding, while also promoting sustainable urban development. Hence, the development of a comprehensive Flood Resilient Design Framework (FRDF) is crucial, integrating architectural adaptation strategies, stakeholder engagement, and policy recommendations. This framework will enhance the city's resilience against future flood events, improving the quality of life for its residents.
- ii. Constructing blue roofs over concrete carports within the compounds of existing buildings to capture and slowly release rainwater and provide insulation. Creating shallow depressions and vegetated channels to capture and filter storm water runoff in estates and communities. Considering the site's topography, drainage patterns, and environmental conditions, Incorporating green roofs, walls, and other BGI features into the building design, Ensuring that BGI features are integrated with other building systems, such as plumbing and electrical systems
- iii. Effective policy frameworks are crucial for supporting the implementation of BGI strategies. The following policy frameworks can encourage BGI adoption and support the creation of more sustainable and resilient communities.

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